

Development Of Jigsaw-Type Cooperative Learning Model Based On Critical Thinking, Communication, Collaboration And Creativity (4c) To Improve Problem Solving Ability In Thematic Learning

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Abstract

This research departs from the learning model that tends to be conventional and has never developed a learning model in teaching and learning activities. This study aims to: (1) produce a product for developing a valid jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity; (2) determine the effectiveness of the application of learning products for the development of a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity carried out by the teacher; and (3) to determine the effectiveness of the product development of a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity in improving problem solving skills. The method that will be used in this study is the 4D developmental research methodology according to Ghiadarajan. The subjects in this study were fifth grade students at SD Negeri 067690 Medan and the object of this research was the 4C-based jigsaw cooperative learning model (Jigsaw-4c). The data collection instruments used consisted of: problem-solving ability tests and observation sheets on the teacher's ability to manage learning. The results showed that: (1) the overall average score on the Assessment and Responses for Model Experts was in the above four categories with "valid" criteria. So it can be concluded that the Assessment and Feedback for Model Experts can be used with minor revisions; (2) The ability of teachers to manage learning with the jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity are in good criteria; and (3) the problem-solving ability of students taught by the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity is higher than the problem-solving ability of students who are taught using conventional learning models.

Introduction

The challenge of developing the Indonesian nation in the 21st century, especially in the field of education, is to prepare a young generation who is flexible, creative, and proactive. The younger generation needs to be formed to be skilled in problem solving, wise in making decisions, think creatively, like to consult, can communicate ideas effectively, and be able to work efficiently both individually and in groups. This is based on the fact that simply knowing knowledge is proven not enough to be successful in dealing with life and life that is increasingly complex and can change rapidly. (Zulela, 2016).

Maftuh (2010), states that to be able to face challenges in the 21st century, one must have a number of skills, namely: (1) critical thinking and problem solving, (2) communicating and collaboration, (3) creativity and innovation, (4) information literacy, (5) media literacy, (6) ICT literacy, (7) flexibility and adaptability, (8) initiative and accountability, (9) leadership and responsibility. Rotherdam & Willingham (2009) noted that the success of a student depends on 21st century skills, so students must learn to have it. Century Skills identifies 21st century skills including: critical thinking, problem solving, communication and collaboration. In line with the previous statements, according to the National Education Association to achieve success and be able to compete in the global community, (Poude et al., 2011).

The demands of the 21st century in the world of education require a shift in educational goals. Namely, preparing students to face a relatively simple, static, and predictable world in the direction of preparing students to live in a world that is not easy to predict and requires high strength of mind and creativity. The Ministry of Education and Culture formulated that the 21st century learning paradigm emphasizes the ability of students to find out from various sources, formulate problems, think analytically and collaborate and collaborate in problem solving. (Nugraha et al., 2015).

To achieve the aims and objectives of learning, students need to be equipped with four dimensions of a comprehensive education program, including: (1) Dimensions of knowledge (Knowledge), (2) Dimensions of skills (Skills), (3) Dimensions of values and attitudes (Values and attitudes), and (4) Dimensions of action (Action) (Halimah, 2018).

Based on the dimensions and learning objectives listed above, learning should not only emphasize mastery of facts at a low level which is very textbook-oriented. Learning should empower students so that all their potential abilities, both knowledge, attitudes, and skills can develop. All of these abilities can be realized in the learning process by involving the full participation of students in learning. The involvement or participation of students in teaching and learning is the basis of development and training for students to participate and work together in social life.

Learning in elementary schools currently seems separated from the real life of students, so it is felt that it is not optimally absorbed by students. In addition, the learning process has not provided adequate opportunities for students to develop the dimensions of the skills they have. Meanwhile, learning at the school level basically aims to prepare students as citizens who master the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that can be used as the ability to solve personal problems or social problems as well as the ability to make decisions and participate in various community activities so that be a good citizen (Abidin, 2012).

Based on the results of preliminary observations regarding the teaching and learning process carried out in the classroom, it shows that creative thinking skills and communication skills as an element of skill dimensions have not been developed optimally. The learning process is more likely to be a process of transferring and absorbing information in the form of curriculum content. In the implementation of learning the teacher is still oriented to the completion of the material. The teacher teaches the subject matter by reading the textbook.

In evaluation activities, the teacher demands that the answers of the students are exactly as he explained. In other words, students are not given the opportunity to think creatively and express their opinions in class. They are used to only taking notes and listening to the teacher's explanation. This is in line with the statement (Prihatmoko, 2016) which states that the profile of students is more in learning behavior to listen to information with dominant teacher activities and teachers take more positions in front of the class which tend to be patronizing rather than teaching students to think about lesson material. The pattern of education in schools causes children to be unable to freely carry out activities according to their will, so that the creative power of children is reduced. (Octavianti & Ratnasari, 2019) explained that research results show that creativity begins to disappear in childhood into adulthood. One of the studies has examined the ability of individuals to come up with original ideas, the comparative value of original answers and the resulting standards.

The importance of developing creative thinking skills in students was stated by (Baharun & Sa'diya Kholifatus, 2018), as follows: First, by being creative, people can manifest themselves. Second, even if someone views that creative thinking skills need to be developed, attention to the development of creative thinking skills is not sufficient, especially in formal education. Third, being creatively busy is not only beneficial but also gives satisfaction to the individual. Fourth, creativity allows humans to improve their quality of life.

Another problem that arises as a form of weakness in the learning process is the teacher's habit of using an "expository" approach. Most teachers teach using the lecture method and expect students to sit, be quiet, listen, take notes and memorize and pit students against each other. (van Alten et al., 2019). The teacher's dominance in the learning process makes students more in a position to listen and receive information. This causes boredom and passivity in students resulting in low communication skills.

This is in line with observations made at SD Negeri 067690 Medan class V in the odd semester of the 2020/2021 academic year, this low communication skill can be seen from the majority of students who do not have the ability to discuss in class, do not dare to argue, respond, answer questions. teachers even though they already have the answers, or ask questions even though they do not understand the questions or problems raised by the teacher. This problem causes students to find it difficult to get information that is useful for their development. In addition, if students are not able to express opinions to others, it can indirectly affect their thinking ability and achievement.

Communication skills are skills that must get more attention from teachers because with these skills students can explore as much information as possible and can convey information orally and in writing. Therefore, every student needs to be trained and given the opportunity to express his understanding and feelings clearly, effectively and creatively. Communication skills can be manifested in the ability to speak, ask questions and listen to others.

As the spearhead in education, it is very important for teachers to understand the characteristics of the material, students and innovative learning models, so that the learning process will be more varied, innovative and constructive and can increase the activity and creativity of students. Therefore, teachers must have strategies to motivate and develop students' thinking skills. This learning strategy must be with the right learning model and be able to have an impact on the dominance of students who are creative, active, innovative, fun atmosphere and develop communication skills.

The ideas obtained by students that are not in the form of perfect solutions can be directed by providing a little help, which is not only assistance through explanations of facts, but also in the form of explanations of concepts or procedures related to the subject matter being taught at the time. that. Another problem is that a person will not be able to prepare himself to solve a problem if the problem is not understood and understood.

To realize 21st century learning, teachers must have good process skills in learning. Process skills can be interpreted as teacher skills in presenting learning that is able to provide a meaningful and enjoyable learning experience for students. Learning is student-centred (student center), and stimulates students to solve problems. The teacher's role in PBM is not only as a source of learning, but also as a facilitator. according to Abidin et al (2017), Process skills are the ability of students to manage those obtained in teaching and learning activities (KBM) which provide the widest opportunity for students to observe, classify, interpret, predict, apply, plan research, and communicate the results of these acquisitions.

In this study, the selected learning model is a jigsaw cooperative learning model which is thought to be able to overcome learning problems. For this reason, the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model is combined with the demands of the 21st century curriculum, namely critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity. The jigsaw type of cooperative learning model is based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity which is assumed to improve students' problem solving abilities. Jigsaw cooperative learning is a learning centered on problem solving skills followed by strengthening creativity and developing problem solving in the learning process (Santayasa, 2007)

Jigsaw cooperative learning is expected to generate interest as well as creativity and motivation of students in learning, so that students can obtain maximum benefits both from the process and learning outcomes. Thus, it is hoped that the learning achievement of students will be better. In this type of jigsaw cooperative learning, students are required to be active so that in learning students are able to bring out their abilities to creatively solve problems that they have not encountered. This is in line with Musfiqon's opinion, good learning is more emphasis on student-centered learning and placing teachers as facilitators, trainers, advisors and intermediaries to get optimal results.

Active means that students do a lot of activities during the learning process, because in jigsaw cooperative learning there are several stages that students must go through during the learning process which include problem clarification, expression of opinions, evaluation and selection and implementation. The activities of students during the learning process are not only listening and taking notes. Asking friends during discussions, daring to express opinions, and other activities both mentally, physically, and socially so that students can use various ways according to their creative power to solve the problem.

Students no longer develop models and strategies in problem situations, but already refer to the steps for solving problems. Students make models to describe problem situations so that the results of modeling at this level are referred to as models of problem situations. Students represent the problem in the form of a problem solving model. At this level, students are very likely to design many models and problem solving strategies that are different from one another.

Thus, researchers see the need to conduct research and development. Development of a jigsaw-based cooperative learning model based on 4c (critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity) in improving problem-solving abilities, where this activity is a learning package with learning strategies and programming of learning materials. teaching and packaged in the form of an integrated module with appropriate learning for use in the classroom.

METHOD

The development model used refers to the 4-D model, proposed by S. Thiagarajan, Dorothy S. Semmel, and Melvyn I. Semmel. According to Thiagarajan, et al. This model consists of four stages, namely defining, designing, developing, and disseminating. Where researchers conduct research that describes the profile of 21st century skills which include critical thinking skills, creative thinking skills, communication skills and collaboration skills in learning jigsaw type cooperative.

This research was conducted at SD Negeri 067690 Medan class V in the odd semester of the 2020/2021 school year. The research was conducted for 3 months or 3 trials, this is because the researchers used the jigsaw type cooperative learning model with the integration of education 21st century skills or termed 4C (Communication, Collaboration, Critical Thinking and Problem Solving, and Creativity and Innovation) so it takes a relatively long time.

The population in this study were fifth grade students of SD Negeri 067690 Medan who were taught using the jigsaw type cooperative learning model based 4C (Jigsaw-4c). The researcher was assisted by the teacher to form groups with each group consisting of 6 heterogeneous students including: 2 high-ability students, 2 moderately capable students, and 2 low-ability students. The researcher used a purposive sampling technique (purposed sample) because there were certain considerations/criteria in choosing the subject selected

as a sample, which was a recommendation from the class teacher, where the level of ability was seen from the value of the last daily test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The learning model developed in this study includes a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity. The development of a jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity there are several supporting devices, the learning tools include i) the validity of lesson plans, ii) the validity of the module, iii) the validity of the test instrument, the development of a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity carried out through: (a) validation by experts, and (b) testing of learning devices, and research instruments carried out using models. Thiagarajan, Dorothy S. Semmel, and Melvyn I. Semmel namely: (1) Identification of learning objectives, namely determining the purpose of the system built to obtain learning after completing the lesson; (2) Conduct learning analysis, which is to determine what abilities are involved in the learning process to achieve goals and analyze the topic or material to be studied. This analysis will produce a diagram of the skills/concepts and show the interrelationships between the skills and concepts; (3) Identification of initial behavior and characteristics, namely determining what minimum abilities the learner must have to complete the tasks.

When analyzing the skills that need to be trained and the stages of the procedures that need to be passed, it should also be considered what skills students already have when they start teaching. In addition, identification is a student-specific characteristic that may have something to do with the design of teaching activities. For example, learners must have reading skills, basic computational skills or verbal and spatial skills. The personality of the learner also influences the design to be made; (4) Writing work objectives, which aim to break down general goals into more specific goals at each stage of learning. At each stage there will be a blend of learning and measurement of learner performance; (5) Develop benchmark reference tests, ie designing test items to provide opportunities for learners to demonstrate the abilities and knowledge stated in the objectives; (6) Developing learning strategies, namely determining instructional activities that help in achieving goals. The strategy will include instructional activities, information delivery, practice and feedback, testing carried out through activities. For example reading, listening, to internet exploration. This instructional activity can be developed by the instructor or the learner may combine newly acquired knowledge with existing knowledge and abilities to form new understanding. The learning process can also be done in groups or individually; (7) Develop and select learning materials; (8) Design and carry out formative evaluation, which aims to provide data for revision and development of instructional materials. In addition, this evaluation is also carried out to collect data that will be used to identify ways to improve teaching. This evaluation can be done, for example by interviewing each student; (9) Revising learning activities, is a constant part of the design process. Revisions are made based on the results of each component of this model. At this stage, the data from the summative evaluation that has been carried out in the previous stage are summarized and analyzed and interpreted to identify the difficulties experienced by students in achieving learning objectives. Likewise, input from the implementation results from experts/validators. It may be that the learning stages are less effective in achieving the final goal, or the activities, teaching materials that have been determined do not help in obtaining the goals; and (10) Design and carry out summative evaluations. Which aims to study the effectiveness of the entire system and is carried out after the formative evaluation stage.

1. Quality jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity

The assessment carried out by the validator includes indicators: format, language, and content of the learning implementation plan. In making revisions, the researcher refers to the results of the discussion by following the suggestions and instructions of the validator. Analysis of the expert validation data on the lesson plan (RPP) found that the average score of each assessment aspect of the five validators gave a value greater than or equal to the "valid" category.

The product validated by the expert consists of (1) an assessment sheet to measure the learning model developed. (2) The written test is in the form of multiple choice to measure knowledge. (3) assessment sheets to measure learning tools and research instruments. The assessment carried out by the validator includes indicators: content validity, question construction, and language. In making revisions, the researcher refers to the results of the discussion by following the suggestions and instructions of the validator. For the results of expert validation on student character, the five validators gave an assessment of the components in the formation of student character with an assessment of the "valid" category. The five validators concluded that authentic assessment instruments could be used.

Thus, it can be seen that all aspects determined to declare a module or device development product valid and effective have been fulfilled, so the development trial to obtain valid and effective learning modules and tools has ended.

2. The effectiveness of the jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity

Learning activities using a jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity Class IV SD Negeri 067690 Medan in learning can be described that the level of active student activity has met the tolerance limit set. This can be seen when the category listen / pay attention to the explanation of the teacher / friend, understand the problems that exist in the student book, and solve problems and find ways or answers to problems. Based on the explanation above, from observing the active activities of students, all categories of observations have met the specified tolerance limits.

The ability of teachers to manage learning using learning tools The jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity which was developed for Class IV SD Negeri 067690 Medan is known that in the aspect of analyzing and evaluating problem solving, the value in this aspect is also caused by values. the indicator value in this aspect is also high. The best indicator is to help students reflect on problem solving. In this case the researcher was able to find out how the results obtained by each group in solving problems, then directing each student in the group to re-check whether the answers found were correct.

Problem Solving Ability of students using the jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity Class V SD Negeri 067690 Medan in learning it can be seen that the Problem Solving Ability of students after learning can be seen from the results of students' work in completing the given test. This problem-solving ability is in the form of student scores from the tests given. Based on the acquisition of student learning outcomes, it is known that classical completeness has reached 86.11%. So that the classical problem-solving ability has been completed.

Device development products are said to be effective if they meet the three indicators above, meaning that based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the Design of Learning Models in the form of Model Books, Teacher Books, Student Books, Learning Plans, and Instruments is a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, effective communication, collaboration, and creativity.

The following describes the results of research on the effectiveness of the development of a jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity.

1. Teacher's Ability in Managing Learning

When viewed from the data analysis of the ability of teachers to manage learning, there is an increase in the ability of teachers to manage learning, namely in the first trial, the value of the ability of teachers to manage learning is in the "good enough" criteria with the average value of 3.8. In the third trial, the teacher's ability to manage learning was in the "good" criteria with an average value of 4.4. Judging from the results of research conducted, the ability to manage learning has increased in trials II and III. The teacher's ability to manage learning is considered quite effective, the teacher is very able to carry out the syntax in the jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity.

If it is associated with theories that examine the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity, then the results of the research above are very reasonable, as stated by Vygotsky (2004: 47) that in a good learning model it emphasizes on scaffolding, namely providing a large amount of assistance in the form of questions when stuck (stagnation of thinking), then reducing the assistance gradually and providing opportunities for students to take on increasing responsibilities as soon as they can do it. Vygotsky also emphasizes the role of the teacher at the stage of giving directive and active questions when there are difficulties experienced by students through direction, encouragement,

From the explanation above, the teacher provides direction to help students dig up information and overcome erroneous or meaningless information, the teacher encourages interaction and collaboration between students, and the teacher's role is to create a mutually respectful learning climate/environment between teachers and students, between students. with fellow students. Parkay (2011: 243) argues that the teacher's role in the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity is only as a facilitator and organizer, namely only regulating student learning activities, providing direction so that the material being studied is easy for students to understand and interpret. The teacher's role as a facilitator is to facilitate and accommodate the diversity of students' abilities.

Learning using a jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity can be used as a reference for the effectiveness of the teacher. This can also be seen from the results of research conducted by Jasmaniah et al (2014), namely: This study uses research and development methods (Research and Development). The results obtained so far in the first year are that 5 (five) steps of the 6 (six) planned steps have been implemented, namely; 1) collect information about the process of learning mathematics in problem-solving aspects that have been carried out by teachers in elementary schools and in lectures, 2) design of teaching materials Cooperative learning model based on jigsaw type 4C (Jigsaw-

4c), 3) design validation aims to assess the design of teaching materials by presenting 2 experts (material experts and media experts) to find out the weaknesses of the designed teaching materials, 4) design improvement of the validation results, 5) trial problem solving teaching materials Cooperative learning model based on jigsaw type 4C (Jigsaw-4c), both limited and broad trials, and 6) revision of teaching materials based on limited and broad trials.

Sanjaya (2008:1) states that one of the problems facing our world of education is the problem of the weakness of the learning process. In the learning process, children are less encouraged to develop thinking skills. The learning process in the classroom is directed at the child's ability to memorize information, the child's brain to remember and hoard various information without being required to understand the information he remembers to relate it to everyday life. In solving problems are very diverse as well. Teachers can overcome this by dividing students into group work consisting of four to five students. So that students can interact and work together, share ideas / ideas in solving problems.

Teachers have competence in managing learning, especially in creating an interesting learning atmosphere in accordance with the role they have. Sanjaya (2006: 21) says that the teacher's role is: (1) the teacher as a learning resource (2) the teacher as a mentor, (3) the teacher as a facilitator, (4) the teacher as a manager, (5) the teacher as a demonstrator, (6) teachers as motivators, (7) teachers as evaluators. Based on the description above, it is natural that the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity can improve the teacher's ability to manage learning.

Success in a learning is determined by how the activity or learning process takes place. Good input and a good learning process can improve learning achievement, furthermore, bad input if given good treatment in the learning process will produce good output. When viewed from student activity, there was an increase in the level of active student activity where in the third trial all categories of observation of student active activity were already within the specified tolerance limit. Student activities in the learning process will cause interaction between teachers and students or fellow students, resulting in a conducive classroom atmosphere, each student involving his or her abilities to the fullest.

In the process of applying jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity with Piaget's theory (Gredler, 2011: 318) states that social interaction in learning activities both with friends in one group and outside the group has a major influence on children's thinking. Through this interaction, children will be able to compare the thoughts and knowledge they have formed with the thoughts and knowledge of others. In another part, John Dewey (Trianto, 2009: 91) explains learning jigsaw cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity is the interaction between the stimulus and the response, is the relationship between the two directions of learning and the environment. The environment provides input to students in the form of assistance and problems, while the brain's nervous system functions to interpret the assistance effectively so that the problem is investigated, analyzed and found a good solution.

Sanjaya (2006: 174) states that learning activities are all actions that are deliberately designed by teachers to facilitate student learning activities such as discussion activities, demonstrations, simulations, conducting experiments, and so on. The activities carried out by the teacher are controlling, leading and directing the learning process, while students as students are required to be active in learning. With the conditions and processes and learning activities above, it is expected to provide opportunities and make students independent learners.

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2. Achievement of Student Problem Solving Ability

After learning using the jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity, the results were 1) The first trial of 18 students, there were 11 students (61.11%) who scored more than or equal to 70% , 2) The second trial showed that from 18 students

there were 15 students (83.33%) who scored more than or equal to 70%, 3) The third trial was obtained that from 36 students there were 31 students (86, 11 %) which scores more than or equal to 70%. This result has exceeded the tolerance limit that has been set, namely at least 80% is in the moderate criteria.

(Jamiah & Surya, 2016) interpreting the learning outcomes obtained by a person after experiencing a learning process within a certain period of time. A learning model is presented as naturally as possible and then students work with problems that require students to apply their knowledge and abilities according to their level of psychological maturity and learning abilities. Arends in (Trianto, 2011:92) argues that a learning approach in which students work on authentic problems with a view to compiling their own knowledge, developing inquiry and higher-order thinking skills, developing independence and self-confidence.

In the learning process it often happens that teachers have difficulty delivering and managing learning so that the lesson seems boring and uninteresting, problems like this usually occur because students cannot understand the subject matter because it does not describe real and concrete conditions in everyday life.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion in this study, several conclusions are put forward as follows:

1. The jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity is effective for improving learning outcomes. Problem Solving Ability using a jigsaw type cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity showed an increase in the achievement of learning outcomes to 86.11%. It also corresponds to the results of the analysis of inferential statistical calculations through the t value for the learning factor of 7.322, it can be concluded that with $t_{table} = 2,042$, with a significance level of 0.000, it can be concluded that $t_{hitung} = 7.322 > t_{table}$. Problem solving skill students who are taught with a jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity are higher than Problem solving skill students who are taught with conventional learning models.
2. The teacher's ability to manage learning with the jigsaw type of cooperative learning model based on critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity is in good criteria with a value of 4.4 which means it has met the established success criteria, which is at least good enough or the NKG value is greater than or equal to 3 (three).

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